

oLIVER STATUS

Aim

The oLIVER project aims to apply APTA-SHAPE to identify biomarkers of NASH for the development of strategies for:

- Early detection of NASH
- Monitoring disease progression and treatment response.

Introduction

Initially, a large library of aptamer nanosensors was created capable of broad-scale targeting of plasma components from blood samples of NASH patients (termed APTA-SHAPE panel training).

1 uL of plasma from 88 blood samples of NASH patients was subsequently profiled to identify aptamer signals becoming upregulated or downregulated in correlation with NASH status (termed APTA-SHAPE sample profiling / branched selection). Plasma components for profiling were immobilized on NHSmagnetic beads.

Aptamer signals are obtained by sequencing of the inherent genetic code and the results of the profiling of each sample. A total of 542.731.580 aptamer reads across the 88 samples were obtained and processed by the software BION by Niels Larsen.

QC analysis

The qq plot shows that the totals are mostly normal distributed, a few samples does not follow the distribution, but overall nothing concerning is seen.

The amount of missing values are calculated on as a function of the rank of the aptamer. As the overall abundance falls the chance of a sequence having a missing value rises. In this case this starts happening around rank 250.

The data shown here is only intended as a training cohort, but to show the potential it is none the less cut into a training and validation dataset of equal size.

To simplify the training cohort, especially considering the now smaller sample sizes in the training and validation set, a new dichotomized category was made "nashown". The samples are put into heavy and mild liver damage. With the criteria of either fibrosis over 1 or steatosis, ballooning or lobular above 2. This is a very rough measure but it is used in the exploratory phase to see if the project merits further investigation.

Differential binding analysis

Each aptamer are now tested for differential binding using a t-test, an aptamer is considered significantly different expressed if the p-value adjusted with Benjamini-Hochberg method was below 0.05. The fold change and p-value are shown in the volcano plot below.

38 aptamers were found to have differential binding between the low and heavy liver damage samples. Only two of these had a higher average binding in the heavy than the low damage, with 36 having a higher average in low than high liver damage.

The significantly differently expressed are visualized in a heat map.

Each column is a sample and each row is an aptamer. We see that for most aptamers they retain the same type of binding for a sample, but the sample are very heterogeneous, even within the same sample type. This may be a consequence of the rough grouping. The same aptamers were tested against a validation dataset.

In the validation dataset we see the same pattern, the aptamers are generally consistent between samples, but the samples are heterogeneous.

Principal component analysis was likewise performed, to serve as a dimensional reduction technique.

For the training data the separation are unsurprisingly strong, with a clear tendency for the nashown TRUE samples having a positive PC1 and the negative samples having a negative PC1.

Looking at the PCA of the validation samples, we see, as expected that the separation are less pronounced, but a separation is still clear. Note that the sign in a PCA is random and the fact that the coordinates of the FALSE-samples are now positive, is a consequence of this randomness.

Another way to visualize the difference between the samples in the PCA is to run a statistical test on the PC1 of the validation data. Since we cannot assume that the coordinates are normally distributed the test used is a Wilcoxon ranked test.

Doing this a p-value of 0.0047 were found between the two categories. Showing a strong statistically significant difference between the NAFLD and NASH samples

Another measure of this difference is ROC curves using the PC1. Doing this a AUC of 0.75 were found. Showing a strong specificity and sensitivity.

Future work

Working on the training cohort it was found that the APTASHAPE technique hold potential to distinguish between the NAFLD and NASH. However looking at the data in more detail, as in the below chart we see that the "FALSE" category can be subdivided into fibrosis = 0 and fibrosis = 1. This indicates that when we get the data from the validation cohort and use the full training cohort for training the models we may be able to build models capturing these more subtle differences.

The experimental work on a validation cohort of 73 samples have already been finished and we are currently waiting for the DNA-sequencing to finish so we can start the data analysis.